

The surface of general ellipsoids

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2015

We view the following figures:

a, b, c = semiaxes of the ellipsoid with $a > b > c$.

It is proved see Schöne [1] p.139 that the ellipsoid's surface F can be written:

$$F = \int_0^{2\pi} -\frac{c}{2} \cdot \left(-\frac{2ab}{c} + \frac{cA^2(u)}{B(u)} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{ab - B(u)}{ab + B(u)} \right) \right) du$$

with

$$A^2 = a^2 \sin^2 u + b^2 \cos^2 u$$

and

$$[B(u)]^2 = a^2 b^2 - c^2 A^2(u)$$

This integral cannot be calculated exactly. We derive a formula. At this formula the influences of the quantities can be seen well. We use Kepler's prismoidal

formula:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} f(x) dx \approx \frac{2\pi}{6} \cdot (f(0) + 4f(\pi) + f(2\pi))$$

We insert the function. With a calculation, see Schöne [1] p.139,140 the following formula is shown:

$$F \approx 2\pi ab - \frac{\pi c^2}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 - c^2}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{a - \sqrt{a^2 - c^2}}{c} \right) + \frac{a}{\sqrt{b^2 - c^2}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 - c^2}}{c} \right) + \frac{4(a^2 + b^2)}{\sqrt{4a^2b^2 - 2c^2(a^2 + b^2)}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{ab\sqrt{2} - \sqrt{2a^2b^2 - c^2(a^2 + b^2)}}{c\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Now we view an example with $a=1.0$ length unit. In the following table are the values of b, c and the surface F :

b	c	F [area units]
0.9	0.8	10.16
0.8	0.7	8.69
0.7	0.6	7.30
0.6	0.5	6.01
0.5	0.4	4.79
0.4	0.3	3.64
0.3	0.2	2.56
0.2	0.1	1.54
0.1	0.05	0.76
0.05	0.01	0.33

References

- [1] Schöne "Differentialgeometrie", 1978, Deutscher-Verlag, Thun